

MAELSTROM

Smart technology for MARine Litter SusTainable
RemOval and Management

D9.2

Final Version of the Plan for Communication and Dissemination

12/2022

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General Information

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Contributing Organizations	All
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Authoring & Approval

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V3	19/12/2022	Isabel Gomes - CIMA	Second Version
V4	21/12/2022	Fantina Madricardo - CNR	Final Version

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Executive Summary

The present document - *Final Version of the Plan for Communication and Dissemination* is Deliverable 9.2. of Work Package 9 of the EU funded project MAELSTROM - *Smart technology for MARine Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management*. The document is an update of Deliverable 9.1. - First Version of the Plan for Communication and Dissemination concluded in June 2021 (month six).

After two years of project activity, we now have a better understanding of the needs and expectations of our audiences, alongside a reinforced network among partners, stakeholders and beneficiaries. This has resulted in improved and better coordinated efforts among the consortium towards common dissemination and communication goals.

In line with the first version of the Plan, the present document is designed to be used both as a guiding document by the consortium's members and as an informative report to the EU, describing the consortium's strategies in promoting public visibility, stakeholder engagement and networking actions around the marine litter issue in Europe and beyond. Despite being structured in two separate pillars, the dissemination and communication efforts complement and articulate mutually: they both work towards achieving visibility and engagement of multiple audiences with the project's mission.

While this Plan describes the goals, audiences and channels applied as part of an overall strategy for dissemination and communication purposes, detailed information on each action can be consulted on the Interim Communication and Dissemination Reports published on month 18, month 36 and month 48.

Table of Contents

GENERAL INFORMATION.....	2
AUTHORING & APPROVAL.....	3
HISTORY OF CHANGES.....	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	4
1 INTRODUCTION TO THE MAELSTROM PROJECT.....	7
2 MAELSTROM CONSORTIUM.....	8
3 AIM OF THE DELIVERABLE.....	9
4 WORK PACKAGE DESCRIPTION.....	10
4.1 TARGET AUDIENCES AND STAKEHOLDERS.....	12
5 DISSEMINATION STRATEGY.....	14
5.1 OBJECTIVES AND EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES.....	14
5.2 DISSEMINATION PLAYERS AND AUDIENCES.....	15
5.2.1 Stakeholder engagement and interplays with third parties.....	18
5.2.2 Capacity Building: audiences and actions.....	23
5.2.3 Participation at strategic events.....	24
5.2.4 Publications on peer-reviews journals.....	26
5.2.5 Participation at the EU Mission and Horizon Results Booster.....	27
6 COMMUNICATION STRATEGY.....	28
6.1 OBJECTIVES AND EXPECTED IMPACTS OF THE COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES.....	28
6.2 COMMUNICATION PLAYERS AND AUDIENCES.....	29
6.3 EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION TOOLS AND CHANNELS.....	32
6.3.1 Project events.....	32
6.3.2 Project website.....	34
6.3.3 Project newsletters and MAELDrops.....	34
6.3.4 Real size plastic whale characters.....	36
6.3.5 Social media channels.....	36
6.3.6 Informative pack.....	37
7 ANNEX 1 - PROJECTS AND INSTITUTIONS ENGAGED WITH MAELSTROM'S ACTIVITIES... 40	

Table of Figures

TABLE 1 - MAELSTROM CONSORTIUM.....	8
TABLE 2: DISSEMINATION PLAYERS, AIMS, TOOLS AND CHANNELS.....	15
TABLE 3: RELEVANT EVENTS & CONFERENCES.....	25
TABLE 4: RELEVANT JOURNALS FOR THE MAELSTROM'S CONSORTIUM.....	26
TABLE 5: MAELSTROM'S COMMUNICATION AUDIENCES.....	30
TABLE 6: MAELSTROM'S EVENTS.....	32
TABLE 7: EU-FUNDED PROJECTS ENGAGED IN MAELSTROM'S ACTIVITIES.....	40
TABLE 8: INSTITUTIONAL ACTORS ENGAGED WITH MAELSTROM'S ACTIVITIES.....	40
TABLE 9: PRIVATE COMPANIES ENGAGED WITH MAELSTROM'S ACTIVITIES.....	40

MAELSTROM

Table of Images

FIGURE 1 - COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TASKS	11
FIGURE 2 - COMMUNICATION PROCEDURES REGARDING INSTITUTIONAL AND IN-KIND THIRD PARTIES' INVOLVEMENT.....	21
22	
FIGURE 3 - COMMUNICATION PROCEDURES REGARDING FINANCIAL THIRD PARTIES' INVOLVEMENT	22
FIGURE 4 - COMMUNICATION PROCEDURES REGARDING THIRD PARTIES' INVOLVEMENT - GRAPHIC REPRESENTATION.....	23
FIGURE 5 - MAELSTROM'S LOGO	38

1 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex question to the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy. MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with full-fledged circular economy and societal oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) sets out a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort marine litter; (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions providing also a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) enhances social awareness about the marine litter issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

2 MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM's consortium consists of the following partners illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1 - MAELSTROM Consortium

	National Research Council	CNR	Project Coordinator Fantina MADRICARDO fantina.madricardo@ismar.cnr.it
Deltares	Deltares	Deltares	Frans BUSCHMAN Frans.Buschman@deltares.nl
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	Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research	CIIMAR	Isabel SOUSA-PINTO ispinto@ciimar.up.pt
	Servizi Tecnici	ST	Nicola FERRARI n.ferrari@stvenezia.com
	The Great Bubble Barrier	TGBB	Philip EHRHORN philip@thegreatbubblebarrier.com
MAKEEN POWER	MAKEEN	MAKEEN	Anders BJORN ABI@makeenenergy.com
	National Center for Scientific Research	CNRS	Marc GOUTTEFARDE marc.gouttefarde@lirmm.fr

3 Aim of the Deliverable

The present document - Final Version of the Plan for Communication and Dissemination - is Deliverable 9.2 of Work Package 9 of the H2020 EU-funded project MAELSTROM - *Smart technology for MARinE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management*.

The document details MAELSTROM's dissemination and communication strategy for the next two years, the period in which the project will come to its conclusion. A First Version of the Plan for Communication and Dissemination was delivered in June 2021 (month six) and presented a preliminary roadmap, now updated thanks to a better understanding of the needs and expectations of our audiences, together with a reinforced network among partners and stakeholders. Moreover, the document reports the measures put in place to address the visibility needs in case of third parties' involvement with the project: this aspect was not initially foreseen in the first version of the Plan however, it represented a positive opportunity to enrich the Plan through a solution achieved in concertation with the consortium.

Alike the first version, the Plan for Communication and Dissemination is intended to be used both as a guiding document by the consortium's members and as an informative report to the EU, describing consortium's efforts to promote MAELSTROM's outcomes and the marine litter issue.

The document is structured in two main pillars: i) the former refers to the *Dissemination Strategy*, meaning ongoing efforts to promote and facilitate the use of MAELSTROM's outcomes among potential users and peers in the fields of research, industry, commercial and policy-making; ii) the latter refers to the *Communication Strategy*, meaning ongoing efforts to create strategic opportunities for promoting the project, its relevance, and milestones to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, engaging in a two-way exchange.

While the present document provides guidelines for visibility, stakeholder engagement and networking, detailed information on each action can be consulted on the Interim Communication and Dissemination Reports published on month 18, month 36 and month 48.

4 Work Package Description

The scope of Work Package 9 (WP9): *Dissemination and Communication* - is to create strategic opportunities for promoting MAELSTROM's approaches and outcomes to a multitude of audiences. Those include potential users and peers within the fields of research, industry, commercial and policymaking, while also engaging the civil society, the media, and the public. Activities under WP9 are formally led by CIMA Research Foundation and supported by the MAELSTROM's consortium, composed of 14 partners from 8 European countries. Partners range from excellence research centres in the fields of marine life, biology, sustainable energy, artificial intelligence and robotics to private multinational and national recycling companies with certified industrial plants. Other partners include a market consultancy company, a micro- enterprise and a marine-litter and plastics orientated NGO. The combination of such different backgrounds and areas of expertise is a strategic asset for MAELSTROM's dissemination and communication efforts.

Despite having chosen, for the scope of clarity, to structure the dissemination and communication efforts in two separated pillars it is important to state that both converge and complement each other to achieve common goals, namely:

1. To increase the **success and reputation** of the MAELSTROM project, highlighting the consortium's identity, efforts, skills, innovations, and project-related initiatives.
2. To draw the attention of multiple stakeholders and audiences regarding **marine litter impacts** on ecosystems and on the existing solutions to mitigate them.
3. To demonstrate the way **MAELSTROM's outcomes can become relevant to our everyday lives**, by introducing novel technologies and improving lives through environmental regeneration, the creation of new market's segments and associated jobs within a circular economy paradigm.
4. To create **market demand** for marine litter removal technologies and recycled products by fostering awareness on marine litter impacts, promoting innovative solutions for litter removal, and highlighting the advantages of recycled products for the industrial supply chain.
5. To develop and deliver **economic feasibility** studies regarding the adoption, functioning and maintenance of MAELSTROM's removal technologies.

MAELSTROM

6. To make good use of findings, by assuring they are taken up by decision-makers in **policymaking**, as well as by industry and the scientific community to ensure follow-up. As part of the efforts to achieve this goal, MAELSTROM has delivered a *Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions regarding Marine Litter* (month 12) as part of Work Package 7. The document is the result of a consultation process among international stakeholders regarding the gaps and opportunities on communication and dissemination efforts of marine litter-related activities. The overarching goal of the document is to contribute towards improved policies and legislations regarding marine litter knowledge, identification, production, removal, and recycling within the European space. The document can be consulted at the EC Cordis website at the following link <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5eea84531&appld=PPGMS>
7. To demonstrate how the European collaboration has produced **scientific excellence**, contributing to solve the societal challenge posed by marine litter on living ecosystems.

Work Package 9 includes five main tasks and specific activity within WP7 (figure 1) also under the leadership of CIMA Research Foundation: the above-mentioned *Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions regarding Marine Litter*, delivered on month 12.

Figure 1 - Communication and Dissemination tasks

- Task 9.1. - Communication and Dissemination Plans
- Task 9.2. - Project Branding & Media
- Task 9.3. - Support Capacity Building Actions
- Task 9.4. - Support Stakeholder Engagement Processes
- Task 9.5. - Support Project's events

4.1 Target Audiences and Stakeholders

Seven audiences and stakeholders' clusters have been mapped while considered to be very relevant to MAELSTROM's scaling, marketization, and outreach efforts, namely:

SCALING

→ Scientific

- Research/Academia and related communities interested in catalyzing scientific research and cooperation towards knowledge and technological development for marine litter identification, removal, and recycling, building upon MAELSTROM's scientific and technological approaches and results.

→ Innovation/Technological

- Technological actors interested to scale up MAELSTROM'S technologies and/or collaborating to improve MAELSTROM's technologies for marine litter removal, sorting, tracking and recycling/regeneration.
- Startups interested in collaborating with the MAELSTROM consortium to improve and/or complement the solutions proposed

→ Donors

- Donors (UN, Private Foundations, National funds) interested in investing in the development of science-based technological solutions for marine litter mitigation - such as the ones proposed by MAELSTROM - and to embed circular economy approaches in everyday life, towards a real sustainable development.

MARKETIZATION

→ Industry

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- Industry suppliers (marine litter processors) interested in processing collected marine litter into second-generation materials to supply productive chains.
- Industry manufacturers (recycled materials consumers) interested in using second-generation/regenerated materials in their productive chains to lower plastic-production and associated carbon impacts.

→ Market

- Market investors interested in scaling and commercializing MAELSTROM's technologies and products.
- Public and Private waste management & recycling companies interested in using MAELSTROM's technologies for increased and improved internal waste management capacities and recycling opportunities.

OUTREACH

→ Civil Society and Media

- Civil society organizations, NGO's and citizens interested in being an active part of the marine litter global challenge, through the adoption of responsible behaviours, political advocacy and collective actions at local level, such as beach clean-ups, awareness-raising events and other related initiatives (glocal concept – think globally, act locally).
- Media actors interested in promoting MAELSTROM's solutions (Seabed Cleaning Platform, Bubble Barrier and MAELSTROM App); interested in creating awareness and advocating for marine litter solutions and circular economy models, from single behaviours to local, national, regional, and international global policies.

→ Policymaking

- Policymakers/Authorities interested in sharing MAELSTROM's vision, solutions and social impacts within their own communities and networks as a sign of their own political involvement and action regarding the marine litter issue.
- EU and EU Working Groups active on the fields of Environmental protection, Plastics and Circular Economy, interested in up taking

consortium's contribution, expertise and outcomes for policymaking and strategic programming in the next decades.

5 Dissemination Strategy

5.1 Objectives and expected impacts of the dissemination activities

MAELSTROM's dissemination strategy refers to ongoing and future efforts to promote and facilitate the use of project's outcomes among potential users and peers within the fields of research, industry, market and policy making. Dissemination activities focus on MAELSTROM's key phases - research, technological development, marketization and impact assessment (environmental, economic and social) - are expected to increase in the following two years, after the implementation and testing phases of MAELSTROM's technologies and the subsequent impact's assessments and findings. Dissemination efforts will highlight:

1. The effectiveness and further opportunities of a multidisciplinary **scientific approach** – combining modeling and field environmental assessments – in identifying marine litter distribution and its impacts on ecosystems.
2. The effectiveness and further opportunities for multidisciplinary scientific approaches to assess the **environmental, economic and social impacts** of removal technologies.
3. The technological advancements regarding automated low-carbon **technologies** for marine litter identification and removal, making use of artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics.
4. The effectiveness of **MAELSTROM's technological solutions** in removing marine litter without creating harmful impacts to ecosystems.
5. The outcomes of technologies' integration for tracking, sorting, and recycling marine litter and converting it into **recycled materials for marketization**.
6. The benefits and **effectiveness of second-generation** products for the industrial supply chains.
7. The **economic and societal impacts** of MAELSTROM solutions through comprehensive life-cycle assessments of both technologies and derived products.
8. The **networking** and interplay with alike projects, initiatives, and stakeholders to accelerate solutions for marine litter mitigation.

MAELSTROM

9. The engagement of **stakeholders and society at large** within the marine litter issue, consequences and single-based mitigation actions.
10. The identification of existing **gaps and strategic activities** to be further developed by the scientific and technological communities working in the marine litter cycle.

MAELSTROM's dissemination activities also contribute to CNR (project coordinator) Third Mission: "*Transferring scientific research to society*".

5.2 Dissemination players and audiences

While CIMA Research Foundation is the Dissemination and Communication work package leader, all partners are expected to contribute to MAELSTROM's outreach efforts within their own specialized networks and sphere of influence. Considering the wide and rich profile of the project, it wouldn't be possible for the CIMA's team alone to reach such vast, skilled and international audiences as the ones so far achieved. Dissemination efforts are concentrated in four clusters:

- (i) Stakeholder engagement and interplays.
- (ii) Capacity-building.
- (iii) Participation at strategic events.
- (iv) Publications on peer-reviews journals.

Dissemination activities are always coordinated with CIMA's team, which supports and assures the compliance with the EU rules and with the MAELSTROM's Plan for Dissemination and Communication. Table 2 describes the consortium's roles on acting the dissemination strategy, alongside the recommended aims, tools and channels used in the process.

Table 2: Dissemination Players, Aims, Tools and Channels

Partner by Audience	Aims	Tools & Channels
<p><u>SCIENTIFIC PLAYERS</u></p> <p>CNR, Deltares, CNRS, TECNALIA, CIIMAR with the support of the EU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote MAELSTROM's scientific approaches and results within the international scientific community. • Contribute to the advancement of the state of the art regarding marine litter mapping, impacts and mitigation strategies. • Make scientific results a common good by openly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific conferences, demonstrative events and fairs on Oceans, Blue Economy, Marine Litter, Robotics, and Artificial Intelligence. • Open-access and peer reviewed publications. • EOOSC platforms. • Memorandums of Understanding with relevant entities.

MAELSTROM

	<p>share data and findings through EOSC and Open Access journals.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen-science magazines (es. Focus), blogs and websites. • Horizon Europe and CORDIS magazines. • EU marine litter networks and projects. • EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” activities. • Institutional website and channels. • MAELSTROM's Web Forum. • MAELSTROM's events website, social media, newsletters, videos.
<p><u>TECHNOLOGICAL PLAYERS</u></p> <p>TECNALIA, CNRS, TGBB, UOM, ISDI, ST, GEES with the support of the EU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disseminate technological advancements regarding MAELSTROM's removal solutions. • Highlight the role of AI and Robotics on answering societal challenges and how is MAELSTROM contributing to it. • Promote technological-based approaches for marine litter identification, removal, sorting, and recycling giving MAELSTROM's example. • Show the benefits of public-private partnerships, sharing MAELSTROM's consortium example. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific conferences, demonstrative events and fairs on Oceans, Blue Economy, Marine Litter, Robotics, and Artificial Intelligence. • EU Research and Innovation events • EU Horizon Results Booster activities • Open-access and peer reviews publications • High-Tech, AI, Robotics and Blue Economy magazines, reports, blogs, and websites. • Expertise networks. • MAELSTROM's Web Forum. • MAELSTROM's events, website, social media, newsletters, videos. • Institutional website and social media channels.
<p><u>INDUSTRIAL PLAYERS</u></p> <p>GEES, MAKEEN with the support of the EU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt and share the benefits of second-generation marine litter products to reduce the environmental impact of the productive chains. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trade associations. • Supply chain networks. • Demonstrative events. • Industry innovation magazine, blogs, and websites. • Institutional website and social media channels. • Horizon Results Booster activities. • MAELSTROM's Web Forum. • MAELSTROM's events, website, social media, newsletters, videos.

MAELSTROM

<p><u>MARKET PLAYERS</u></p> <p>ALPHA UK, TECNALIA with the support of the EU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sponsor and disseminate the socio-economic benefits of MAELSTROM's blue and circular economic solutions. • Create market demand for MAELSTROM's technologies, especially within public and private waste management and recycling companies. • Identify new stakeholders and new geographic regions where MAELSTROM's technologies could be successfully accepted and implemented. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Horizon Results Booster activities. • Sector-specific networks, conferences, and events. • Institutional website and social media channels. • Economic and Innovation magazines, reports, blogs, and websites. • MAELSTROM's Web Forum. • MAELSTROM's events, website, social media, newsletters, videos.
<p><u>POLICY PLAYERS & DONORS</u></p> <p>All partners with support from EU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reinforce knowledge and data on marine litter impacts in coastal ecosystems. • Promote MAELSTROM's solutions on mitigating the marine litter issue. • Identify gaps, opportunities, and best practices of marine litter mitigation initiatives worldwide. • Propose and foster science-based policy making and legislation regarding marine litter. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science-police interface conferences at local, national, and regional levels. • Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions (WP7). • EU /UN Plastics working groups. • Horizon Europe and CORDIS magazines. • Institutional website and social media channels • MAELSTROM's Web Forum. • MAELSTROM's events, website, social media, newsletters, videos. • Contribution to EU and UN White/Green papers. • Contribution to the Plastics/Marine Litter Policy Strategy application.

MAELSTROM

<p><u>CIVIL SOCIETY PLAYERS</u></p> <p>CIMA, VLPF, CNR, ISDI, TGBB, CIIMAR, TECNALIA with the support of the EU</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reinforce the global scale of the marine litter issue, its impacts for living ecosystems and MAELSTROM's contribution for its mitigation. • Promote a circular economy model by demonstrating that marine litter can be reduced and transformed into a new and useful resource. • Engage citizens in responsible behaviours, with a focus on plastics consumption and disposal. • Show the EU efforts in developing and implementing blue, green and circular economy approaches, and its benefits to our everyday lives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society dedicated events such a clean ups, info days and public talks. • Partnerships with pilot areas local schools and associations for marine and environmental protection, including surf groups. • Institutional website and social media channels • MAELSTROM's events, website, social media, newsletters, videos, and informative materials.
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5.2.1 Stakeholder engagement and interplays with third parties

Stakeholder engagement and synergies with alike EU funded projects and with public and private entities – including scientific and technological centers, industrial plants, waste management companies, recycling enterprises and private donors - are a fundamental part of the dissemination strategy and will keep playing a predominate role as part of future efforts. Partners are invited to establish fruitful contacts and synergies within their own networks, promoting MAELSTROM and its activities and when possible, to establish formal agreements for collaborative actions. Agreements so far established among MAELSTROM's, and relevant stakeholders include:

- a Memorandum of Understanding with the Italian Ecopolietilene consortium (<https://ecopolietilene.it/>). Ecopolietilene is an autonomous, non-profit consortium recognized by the Italian Ministry of the Environment, Land and Sea Protection made up of manufacturers, distributors, and recyclers of polyethylene goods. Ecopolietilene provided the recycled plastic material from which MAELSTROM's real size sperm whales were built.

MAELSTROM

- A Memorandum of Understanding between the University of Bologna and Tecnalio for the mentorship of a PhD student at Tecnalio's headquarters.
- Open collaboration among MAELSTROM and the EU funded project In-No-Plastic (under the same call) has so far translated into an active communication synergy through shared social media posts, press releases, and organization of common events.
- Several EU-funded projects and groups working in the marine litter field have been contacted by the consortium and have participated at MAELSTROM's workshops. ANNEX 1 reports a list of engaged projects and institutions with whom we are currently collaborating.
- Waste management companies of Venice (Veritas) and North of Portugal (Lipor) are actively engaged with the MAELSTROM's team, participating at dedicated meetings for the local implementation of MAELSTROM's removal and its processing. Other important institutional and private actors are described on ANNEX 1.
- Our partner The Great Bubble Barrier has received funding support from Engie Foundation for the implementation of the Bubble Barrier in Vila do Conde

Other potentially strategic and useful tools for stakeholders' engagement are the MAELSTROM's Interactive Forum – hosted by the MAELSTROM's website - and MAELSTROM's thematic webinars, both outcomes of Work Package 7, led by partner CIIMAR. The Interactive Forum and Thematic Webinars address key topics regarding marine litter research, initiatives and policies happening in Europe and beyond and represent important platforms to gather inputs and to engage stakeholders. CIMA's team was in charge of setting the IT infrastructure to host the Interactive Forum and to train CIIMAR's colleagues on its access and maintenance. Both activities have been successfully conducted.

Forum's topics include:

- Marine litter impacts on environmental and human health and the role of civil society to tackle the marine litter challenge.
- Strategies and innovative modelling to track ML and identify hotspots.
- Innovative technologies and solutions to collect and remove ML from the coastal ecosystems.
- Marine Litter and Circular Economy: Sort and Recycling ML.
- Exploitation of regenerated products: best practices.

Action Plan for MoUs and official engagement with the project:

1 – Before officially engaging MAELSTROM with a third-party entity the partner is requested to inform the Project Coordinator of its intentions and to fill the MS Teams spreadsheet on the dedicated MAELSTROM channel.

2 - The Project Coordinator will assess the existence of ethical issues or possible conflicts of interest; if needed the Project Coordinator might ask the consortium members and/or the Steering Committee to meet and discuss the partner's proposal.

3 – Depending on the type of engagement established (institutional/monetary/in kind) the partner shall follow the "*Communication and Dissemination Procedures Regarding Third Parties involvement*", approved by the consortium in 21/01/2022 (see below, point 5.2.1.1).

5.2.1.1 Communication and dissemination procedures regarding third parties' involvement

The rationale behind the definition of common procedures for third parties' involvement was based on classifying the type of parties - institutional or private - and assessing if their involvement was bringing a benefit to a group of partners or only to a single partner. After a consultation process among partners the procedures were structured as follows:

i) Institutional and In-Kind Parties: action plan

If considered to benefit a foreseen action and **group of partners**, every institutional/in-kind support can be fully acknowledged on communication materials. If requested, either by the third party or by the affiliated partner, third party's logos can be placed on MAELSTROM's communication materials (ex. Venice or Porto Municipalities logos), tagged on social media, and mentioned on press releases and in relevant project's events and activities. Advanced approval will need to be previously given by the Project Manager/Consortium.

If considered that the institutional/in-kind support offered benefits **only one partner**, the communication process shall occur independently from MAELSTROM's communication group and shall be led by the affiliated partner responsible for the

agreement. In this case, if the support received by the partner will be used for MAELSTROM-related activities, the project name and the European Union co-financing shall be acknowledged, without creating a visual association (no logos together). In case the partner uses the support received for activities that do not relate to the MAELSTROM project, no mention to the project or the European Union shall be made.

Figure 2 - Communication procedures regarding institutional and in-kind third parties' involvement

ii) Monetary/Financing Third Parties

If considered to benefit a **group of partners**, every monetary/financial support can be fully acknowledged on communication materials. If requested, either by the third party or the affiliated partner, third party's logos can be placed on MAELSTROM's communication materials, tagged on social media and mentioned on press releases or in relevant project's events and activities. Approval will need to be previously given by the Project Manager/Consortium.

If considered to benefit only a **single partner**, the communication process shall occur independently from MAELSTROM's communication strategy and shall be led by the affiliated partner responsible for the agreement. If the support received by the partner is to be used for MAELSTROM-related activities, the project name and the European Union co-financing percentages shall be acknowledged, without

creating a visual association (no logos together). Moreover, the partner benefiting from the monetary support shall clearly state the co-funding proportion being received, based on the total funding received by the European Union within the MAELSTROM project. In the case that the partner uses the support received for activities not related to the MAELSTROM project, no mention to the project or the European Union shall be made.

Figure 3 - Communication procedures regarding financial third parties' involvement

Figure 4 - Communication procedures regarding third parties' involvement - Graphic representation

5.2.2 Capacity Building: audiences and actions

Capacity-building actions were designed to reinforce MAELSTROM's outreach and the efficient use its proposed technologies, namely: the Seabed Cleaning Platform, the Bubble Barrier and the MAELSTROM App. The role of CIMA's team within these activities is to provide the necessary support and informative materials - brochures, videos and graphics - to facilitate the information transfer and the capacity building processes within three target groups:

- **MAELSTROM's Communication Focal Points:** a capacity-building workshop focusing on Communication and Stakeholder Engagement was expected to happen during the kickoff meeting in February 2021. However, considering the constraints on interaction imposed by a 3-day virtual meeting and the need to build a common and continuous ground among communication focal points, CIMA's team has proposed to replace the one-off capacity-building workshop with regular dissemination and communication e-meetings (starting in February 2021). During meetings partners have the chance to align on main milestones, events, and future actions, as well as to make requests and

MAELSTROM

or/discuss ideas relevant to project's outreach. From October 2022 our Project Coordinator (CNR-ISMAR) as suggested to convert the dissemination and communication meetings into general project meetings so to update partners on all project activities. The suggestion was widely accepted. A summary of the contents of the meetings is described on Table 5, under the Internal Communication section.

- **MAELSTROM App Users:** capacity building workshops happen “on field”, during clean-ups and info-days in Portugal and Italy. Users include environmental associations, volunteers, and marine litter practitioners. The app is not designed for the general public, as it requires some knowledge regarding the different categories of plastics' classification.
- **Operators of MAELSTROM technologies:** capacity building workshops on how to operate and maintain MAELSTROM's Seabed Cleaning Platform and the Bubble Barrier are expected to happen in the pilot locations of Venice and Vila do Conde, targeting waste management companies and municipalities for a sustainable use of the machinery and their associated processes.

Action Plan:

1 – Capacity building for partners: CIMA to organize monthly meetings based on partners' availability assessed through doodle. CIMA to propose meetings' topics and to invite partners to present their recent communication and dissemination experiences, leaving free time for interaction and requests.

2 - Capacity building activities for App Users and Operators: CIMA's team produces a series of informative materials – brochure, videos, graphics - to support partners on disseminating main technological features. The material is co-designed among CIMA's team and the partners in charge of the technological development so to assure accurateness of information.

5.2.3 Participation at strategic events

External conferences and events are attended by consortium members as a way to share acquired knowledge on MAELSTROM's themes and as a way to foster stakeholders' interest and interaction towards the project. MAELSTROM's partners use their participation in external events as an additional opportunity to establish synergies with other initiatives having similar or complementary scopes. All partners

MAELSTROM

look, suggest and participate at major events in their own fields of expertise and promote the work developed within the MAELSTROM project. A complete list of attended events during the first 18 months of MAELSTROM's activities can be accessed at the following link:

Deliverable 9.3: First Interim Communication and Dissemination Report concluded on month 18 and available at the link:

<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5eea84531&appId=PPGMS>

Table 3: Relevant Events & Conferences		
Name	Link	Date
UN Water Conference	https://www.unwater.org/news/un-2023-water-conference	New York, 22-24/03/2023,
International conference on Robotics & Automation - ICRA	https://www.ieee-ras.org/conferences-workshops/fully-sponsored/icra https://www.icra2023.org/	London, 29/05-02/06/2023
		2024 - TBA
IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)	https://www.ieee-ras.org/conferences-workshops/financially-co-sponsored/iros	Detroit, 29/09/2023 - 06/10/2023
		2024 - TBA
ECOMONDO	https://www.ecomondo.com/	Rimini, 7-10/11/2023
		2024 - TBA
GEOHAB2023	https://geohab.org/geohab-2023/	La Reunion, 5-12 May, 2023

Action Plan:

1. Partners inform the Dissemination and Communication Coordinator (CIMA) and the Project Coordinator (CNR-ISMAR) regarding their participation at a specific event.
2. Partners to send a short text providing detailed information on their participation, with relevant topics, links and presentation to be used.
3. CIMA to provides support, when requested, through the provision of MAELSTROM's informative materials and templates. If relevant, depending on the event profile, CIMA might produce press releases and activate specific media contacts.

MAELSTROM

4. CIMA to announce and disseminate the participation at events on MAELSTROM's website and social media channels.

5.2.4 Publications on peer-reviews journals.

Over the project duration, project partners commit to release scientific publications on MAELSTROM's findings and impacts. Despite the fact that this activity does not depend on CIMA's team, full support is provided when requested to facilitate the scientific publications and their outreach. Table 3 lists relevant scientific journals for MAELSTROM's consortium.

Title	Website	Publisher	Impact Factor
Frontiers in Marine Science	https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/marine-science	Frontiers Media S.A.	3.661
Environmental Science: Water Research and Technology	https://www.rsc.org/journals-books-databases/about-journals/environmental-science-water-research-technology/	Royal Society of Chemistry	3.449
Monitoring of Mediterranean Coastal Areas	https://media.fupress.com/files/pdf/24/4402/15016	Firenze University Press	Catalogue
Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology	https://www.tandfonline.com/loi/best20	Taylor and Francis Ltd.	8.3
Resources, Conservation and Recycling	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/resources-conservation-and-recycling	Elsevier Ltd.	8.086
GCB Bioenergy	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/17571707	Wiley-VCH Verlag	5.316
IEEE Transactions on Robotics	https://www.ieee-ras.org/publications/t-ro	IEEE	6.123
IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=3516	IEEE	5.673
Mechanism and Machine Theory	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/mechanism-and-machine-theory	Elsevier	3.312
Sensors	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sensors	MDPI	3.275
Biomass and Bioenergy	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/biomass-and-bioenergy	Elsevier	3.551
Energy Strategy Reviews	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/energy-conversion-and-management-x	Elsevier	3.895
Journal of Hazardous Materials	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-hazardous-materials	Elsevier	14.224

MAELSTROM

Science of the Total Environment	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/science-of-the-total-environment	Elsevier	10.753
Chemosphere	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/chemosphere	Elsevier	8.943
Marine Pollution Bulletin	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/marine-pollution-bulletin	Elsevier	7.001
Toxics	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/toxics	MDPI	4.472
Remote Sensing	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/remote-sensing	MDPI	5.349

Action Plan:

1. Each time partners identify a relevant Call for papers/articles to which they wish to participate they shall communicate it to the Project Coordinator (CNR-ISMAR) which might invite other partners to join.
2. Before submitting a scientific publication, partners are invited to send a draft version to all the consortium members. According to Art. 29 of the Annotated Model Grant Agreement of the European Commission. (V2.0.1, May 2015) "Beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of - unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate."
3. Therefore, "Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests."
4. According to Art. 29 of the Annotated Model Grant Agreement of the European Commission. (V2.0.1, May 2015) "Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results."
5. In coordination with the article's authors, CIMA will translate the scientific publication into an informative article to be disseminated across multiple channels (website, social media, networks).
6. All partners contribute to the promotion and dissemination of the various publications.

5.2.5 Participation at the EU Mission and Horizon Results Booster

As part of its social commitment and dissemination activities MAELSTROM has joined the European Commission's Charter of the [Mission Restore our Oceans and](#)

MAELSTROM

[Waters 2030](#). MAELSTROM supports the Mission in several ways, by acting on the protection of aquatic ecosystems and on pollution prevention through its innovative marine litter removal and recycling technologies. In carrying out these actions under the Mission Charter, MAELSTROM commits to support the [EU Ocean Knowledge System](#) and comply with FAIR principles on data and knowledge. In addition, MAELSTROM will involve citizens and will share expertise and experiences with other actors participating at the Mission, so to collectively achieve the Mission's goals.

Moreover, MAELSTROM is adhering to the free-of-charge EU services of the [Horizon Results Booster](#). The services are provided by experts and cover several paths in Dissemination and Exploitation activities, notably Portfolio Dissemination and Exploitation, Business Plan Development, and Go to Market services. As part of MAELSTROM's marketization efforts, with the support of our partner Alpha UK and the Horizon Results Booster we aim at building a portfolio on MAELSTROM's technologies - removal devices and App - to be presented to relevant stakeholders, donors and/or adopters as part of a long-term sustainability vision of the project and of the marine litter issue mitigation.

6 Communication Strategy

6.1 Objectives and expected impacts of the communication activities

The communication strategy refers to ongoing and future efforts to create strategic opportunities for promoting the MAELSTROM project, its relevance, and milestones to a multitude of audiences - including the media and the public - engaging in a two-way exchange.

In support to the described dissemination activities, broad communication actions are undertaken aimed at promoting MAELSTROM's goals, activities and findings in a clear and intelligible way. In alignment to the UN Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, the 2030 Agenda and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSDF), MAELSTROM's communication efforts also focus on raising awareness regarding marine litter dynamics, associated impacts and solutions. Special attention is given to plastic consumption and disposal behaviours. Main communication objectives are:

MAELSTROM

- To support MAELSTROM's dissemination efforts, through communicative materials and actions.
- To promote wide visibility of MAELSTROM's goals, milestones, technologies and events.
- To promote international legislations and frameworks on Plastics and Sustainable Oceans such as the European Marine Strategy Framework, the Single-use Plastic Directive (SUP), the SDG Life Bellow Water and the EU MISSION: *Restore our Oceans and Waters* to which MAELSTROM has officially joined during 2022.
- To raise public awareness on marine litter and responsible behaviours within civil society at large, with focus on schools and young generations

YOUNG GENERATIONS

Young generations are key for the adoption of sustainable development models such as circular economy. Within MAELSTROM and thanks to our partners CNRS-ISMAR, Venice Lagoon Plastic Free and CIIMAR, schools in Venice and Porto's region are often engaged in MAELSTROM's clean up events, info days and awareness raising events. Other forms of young generations involvement have been widely supported by the MAELSTROM project: through our Project Coordinator CNR-ISMAR, we have participated at the BlueMed Hackathon 2021, a student-team challenge to develop ideas and solutions for a Healthy Plastic Free Mediterranean Sea and to promote sustainable blue growth and circular bioeconomy in the Mediterranean.
(<http://www.bluedmed-initiative.eu/bluedmed-hackaton/>).

6.2 Communication players and audiences

Although CIMA Research Foundation bears leadership of communication activities, several partners support and pro-actively engage in these efforts. Strong linkages with the partner Venice Lagoon Plastic Free (Italy), leading the In-No-Plastic communication activities and with vast experience on plastic public awareness events, are in place and expected to continue throughout the project duration. Linkages with CNR-ISMAR's (Italy) and CIIMAR's (Portugal) past and present activities in the plastics field, alongside initiatives with schools in Venice and Porto are part of partners' efforts to create plastic-awareness and to promote MAELSTROM's. Synergies with those partners, coming from the same geographic areas as the pilot

MAELSTROM

areas, expand MAELSTROM's visibility and increase the engagement of local communities with contents being transmitted in national languages (Italian and Portuguese).

Citizens, Young Generations and Local Administrations are specially targeted during clean up events and info days, during which the MAELSTROM's team reinforces awareness on marine litter accumulation and single-preventive behaviours to avoid further environmental damages and societal costs. Audiences are invited to think about plastic production and waste, with a sense of civic responsibility and with a circular economy vision. This is achieved not only during public events/info days, but also through the publication of our MAELDrops: illustrated e-postcards with information regarding the impact of marine litter and plastic pollution, published on social media every 2 months. These actions together are expected to change the way audiences perceive marine litter, and how themselves can be an active part for sustainable oceans and societies.

Table 5: MAELSTROM's Communication Audiences

Segment	Goal
<u>RESEARCH/ACADEMIA</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To demonstrate the effectiveness of MAELSTROM's approaches for marine litter identification, environmental assessments, and technological solutions to sustainably remove, sort, and recycle marine litter. To promote the EU efforts and the EU Missions in the field, opening a space for dialog and collaboration among research communities in the marine litter field.
<u>TECHNOLOGICAL/INDUSTRIAL</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To demonstrate the effectiveness of MAELSTROM's technological solutions to sustainably remove, sort, and recycle marine litter, promoting its scale up at industrial levels. To promote the adoption of plastic's second-generation materials in the industrial supply chain.
<u>FUNDERS/SUPPORTERS</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To demonstrate the effectiveness of MAELSTROM's technological solutions to sustainably remove, sort, and recycle marine litter, promoting its continuously improvement and its implementation in other geographic areas where funding is needed.
<u>DECISION/POLICY MAKERS</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To demonstrate the effectiveness of MAELSTROM's technological solutions to sustainably remove, sort, and recycle marine litter, promoting its adoption. To highlight the need for policies to reduce the impact of marine litter accumulation and to demonstrate their efficacy through the promotion of best practices.

MAELSTROM

<u>CIVIL SOCIETY</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To create a culture of awareness regarding marine litter impacts on coastal ecosystems and to promote a shift in consumers behaviour towards decreasing the consumption and generation of new potential marine litter. • To promote a circular economy paradigm, alongside the scientific and technological advancements in the field and the EU efforts towards it. • To empower citizens to become ambassadors of the marine litter issues, by advocating for better policies and by joining civil movements
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MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic collaboration

Since the beginning of the project, MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic, another EU-funded project under the same call (ID: H2020-FNR-2020 - *Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter*), have closely collaborated specially. This is possible thanks to the participation of partner Venice Lagoon Plastic Free in both projects.

MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic both contribute to the goal of the **UN Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development** aiming at “*a clean ocean where sources of pollution are identified and removed*”. This collaboration is particularly relevant for stakeholder’s engagement, communication, and dissemination efforts. The benefits of having a common task force among the two teams are multiple:

- Creation of synergies among both projects towards disseminating a culture of **awareness** regarding marine litter impacts on coastal ecosystems, within pilot areas and beyond.
- Promotion and visibility of both project’s innovative technological solutions for the removal and recycling of marine litter, within a sustainable circular economy approach.
- Optimization of **resources**, ideas, creativity, and efforts among both projects’ communications teams.
- Be a living example of collaboration among EU-funded projects working towards a common goal - *to tackle the marine litter*.

6.3 External communication tools and channels

MAELSTROM's communication efforts have been reflected on a series of products and channels designed to share and promote MAELSTROM's vision and to facilitate the involvement of peers, stakeholders and civil society at large.

Considering the wide exposure of MAELSTROM's actions, fueled by the visibility of some of the consortium's members, CIMA's team has significantly invested on the design and production of external communication products and actions, such as:

- Project events and media coverage
- Project website
- Project newsletters and MAELDROPS
- Real size recycled plastic whale characters
- Social media channels
- An informative pack

6.3.1 Project events

MAELSTROM's organized events were designed to facilitate brainstorming and exchange of ideas and feedbacks among participants, a vital exercise to redirect and reinforce project's vision, actions and outcomes. Events include internal meetings, workshops, clean-ups, info-days and demonstrative events. In total, twenty-one dissemination events will be directly organized by the MAELSTROM's consortium during project's lifetime as illustrated in Table 6. Despite the COVID-19 pandemic situation, MAELSTROM's events were so far implemented with no constraints, being adapted to hybrid formats when possible.

Table 6: MAELSTROM's Events

	Title	Date
Kick-off Meeting	MAELSTROM Kick Off Meeting	03-04-05.02.2021
MAELSTROM's Workshops	Workshop: Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy joint event with In-No-Plastic H2020 project	03.06.2020
	Workshop: Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy, joint event with InNoPlasticsH2020 project	06/2022
	Workshop: Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy Challenges and Opportunities - Venice, Italy, joint event with In-No-Plastic H2020 project	06/2023

MAELSTROM

	MAELSTROM Final Workshop & Conference – Porto, Portugal	2024
Clean ups & Info Days	Yearly clean-up & Info Day - Venice, Italy on World Ocean/World Environmental Day	06.2021 06.2022 06.2023 06.2024
	Yearly clean-up & Info Day - Porto, Portugal on World Clean Up Day	09.2021 09.2022 09.2023 09.2024
	Yearly clean-up & Info Day – San Sebastian, Spain	09.2022 06.2023
Demonstration Events	Yearly side events - Venice, within the International Venice Boat Show	06.2022 06.2023 06.2024
	Side event – Porto, at the Business2Sea	11.2023

Action Plan:

1. Partners responsible for the organization of events are invited to set a specific working group two months before the event venue. The working group shall include CIMA's team to follow up and support the dissemination and communitarian aspects of the event.
2. CIMA to provide guidelines, suggestions and support according to partner's needs and requests.
3. Event's materials shall follow the EU and MAELSTROM's dissemination and communication guidelines, regarding visual identity, third parties' involvement and media outreach. Partners are invited to send their materials to CIMA's communication team to get approval. CIMA does not assume any responsibility for communication products produced without its supervision.
4. Press releases are prepared either by the organizing partner(s) and by CIMA's team, in coordination with the Project Coordinator. Partners are asked to translate press releases in their own language and further disseminate to local media channels.
5. Media coverage will be led by the organizing partners and CIMA by contacting local, regional and international media channels.
Press reviews are archived and displayed on MAELSTROM's website:
<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-press-review/>

MAELSTROM

6.3.2 Project website

MAELSTROM's website aims at providing an easy and open access to project's information, goals and activities to all sorts of audiences. Parallely, the website works as a repository for informative products such as posters, ppt presentations and roll ups templates, downloadable under the Media section. The website is divided in five sections and regularly updated, according to project's own activities and milestones, giving users the possibility of following events, subscribing to the MAELSTROM's newsletter, and registering to participate at the Interactive Forum, led by our partner CIIMAR. Search Engine Optimization (SEO) parameters have been applied to guarantee straightforward access and visibility to project's website. A new subsection "Data Management and Sharing" has been added in September 2022, under the section "About" detailing how is MAELSTROM following a FAIR (Findable, Accessible Interoperable and Re-usable) data structure.

Link: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/>

Action Plan:

1. Partner(s) to inform the Communication Coordinator (CIMA) regarding relevant activities and events, at least one week in advance.
2. CIMA to interview/interact with partner(s) and decide on the best communication and dissemination outputs (ex. interview, news, post, press release...), in coordination with the Project Coordinator (CNR-ISMAR).
3. CIMA to proceed with the selection and publication of the final piece, approved by the relevant partner and by the Project Coordinator.
4. All other partners to support and contribute to the outreach efforts by and sharing contents with their own institutions.

6.3.3 Project newsletters and MAELDrops

Biannual newsletters, starting in June 2021, are sent to partners, stakeholders, and registered users. Newsletters contain information on MAELSTROM's activities and milestones, including project's highlights and participation at past and future relevant events. It is possible to subscribe to MAELSTROM's newsletter by filling in the dedicated form on the project website (homepage). Data protection on subscription is guaranteed in accordance with GDPR from 2018.

MAELSTROM

Newsletters archive: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstrom-newsletters/>

Aiming at making topics on marine litter, plastic pollution, circular economy, and recycling innovations accessible to as many people as possible, CIMA's team has created an editorial project called MAELDrops: short "pills" of information accompanied under the form of illustrated digital postcards on topics such as research findings on marine litter, plastic types and preventive behaviours. MAELDrops are published on social media and on MAELSTROM's website on average every 2 months; they were not initially foreseen when writing the project proposal but have become an important tool to support MAELSTROM's awareness goals. Sources of information to feed the MAELDrops come from scientific papers, reports by the EU, UN and accredited websites.

Action Plan Newsletter:

1. CIMA to collect relevant information regarding MAELSTROM's activities on the previous and future six months-period.
2. CIMA to produce a first newsletter draft and to share it with the Project Coordinator and the Communication Focal Points.
3. CIMA to collect suggestions and convey them into a final newsletter version.
4. CIMA to publish and send the newsletter through MailChimp to all partners and registered users.
5. CIMA to publish the newsletter on MAELSTROM's website and social media as a way to increase outreach and to invite new users to register to the newsletter service.

Action Plan MAELDrops:

1. CIMA do propose a relevant topic and to draft a MAELDrop text.
2. CIMA to send the draft to the partner with more expertise on the chosen topic for revision.
3. Partner to send feedback to CIMA within three working days.
4. CIMA to graphically illustrate and to publish the final piece

6.3.4 Real size plastic whale characters

As part of MAELSTROM's communication activities, three life-size whales were delivered to Portugal (1) and Italy (2) and showcased during the 2021 and 2022 clean-up events in the Porto Region and during MAELSTROM's *International Workshop on the Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy*, held in Venice during the International Boat Show in June 2022. The team is now looking for a suitable long-term location for the third whale, ensuring that it will be used as an educational tool to raise young generation awareness on the impacts of marine litter.

The three real-sized plastic sperm whale installations were created with recycled polyethylene provided by the Ecopolietilene consortium with whom the project has established an MoU, as part of its stakeholder engagement strategy. The reason for choosing a sperm whales (*Physeter macrocephalus*) as mascots for our project is due to the fact that sperm whales, like other marine mammals, are endangered and particularly threatened by plastic marine litter: dozens of these whales die every year due to inflammation caused by the presence of indigestible plastic in their stomach or due to entanglement in ghost (plastic-made) nets. Nets are often made of polyethylene, a non-biodegradable material, which uses a considerable amount of fossil fuels to be produced and takes centuries to decompose, being therefore imperative to reduce its use and to recycle it as much as possible.

Action Plan:

1. CIMA to produce, deliver and assembly the three whale models to partner's locations; suitable locations are to be indicated by the local partner, responsible for the whale maintenance during the project duration.

6.3.5 Social media channels

Social media are a fast and effective channel to reach multiple audiences, independently of their geographic areas, and represent the main communication channel of the MAELSTROM project. Our scopes within social media are triple: i) to disseminate MAELSTROM's scientific and technological developments, outcomes and impacts; ii) to foster awareness on marine litter impacts, single-use plastics and circular economy living models; iii) to promote the EU efforts, legislation and frameworks to tackle the marine litter issue.

MAELSTROM

MAELSTROM's social media accounts include: i) LinkedIn; ii) Facebook; iii) Twitter; iv) Instagram and v) YouTube, entirely managed by CIMA's team, with inputs from partners. The social media plan foresees an average of two posts a week on main MAELSTROM's activities – from research findings to participation at conferences, clean-up activities and webinars. Within each post the full consortium is tagged, alongside organizing entities, third parties and relevant EU/UN agencies. The aim is to let partners and the EU/UN to know about MAELSTROM's activities and its commitment to communicate, acknowledge and engage reach growing audiences. Consortium partners are invited to interact and re-publish MAELSTROM posts, whenever possible.

EU/UN agencies relevant for MAELSTROM's posts are EU Mare, EU Climate Action; EU Science and Innovation, EU Dissemination Media Agency, EU Green Research and United Nations Ocean Decade.

Hashtags to accompany posts are updated following trending topics and include: **#marinelitter #sustainableblueeconomy #circularconomy #plasticpollution #plasticfree #sdg14 #beatplasticpollution**

Action Plan:

1. Partners to keep CIMA's team aware of activities and participations at MAELSTROM related events.
2. CIMA to develop a post content and in case of necessity to review it with relevant partner(s).
3. CIMA to publish the final content on the most relevant social media accounts.

6.3.6 Informative pack

Considering the wide range of events at which MAELSTROM participates, an informative pack was designed and produced to support partners and to maintain a coherent project identity. All materials are available and downloadable through internal platforms such as Seeds, Microsoft Teams and the MAELSTROM's website, under the media section: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstorm-media-kit/>

6.3.6.1 Logo

MAELSTROM's logo was designed by a professional designer and represents the key project elements; the logo was studied to perform well in multiple settings and colors, from traditional paper printing to T-Shirts, web, App and gadgets.

Figure 5 - MAELSTROM's logo

6.3.6.2 Power Point and Word Templates & Presentation

Visually coordinated Power Point and Word templates, following the EU graphic rules, have been developed for internal and external presentations and report activities. Partners are invited to use exclusively those templates when presenting MAELSTROM activities. An official Project Presentation was also created using Power Point, highlighting the main MAELSTROM's features.

6.3.6.3 Event's materials

A MAELSTROM's event's kit was designed to adapt to formal (e.g., conferences) and informal events (such as clean-ups). It includes internal and external roll-ups, trilingual brochures, flags, T-shirts, and bags which are openly available to the consortium's partners through the dedicated MS Teams channel, the SeedsDMS

MAELSTROM

repository and on the MAELSTROM website, under the media section (<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/dissemination-items/maelstorm-media-kit/>).

Printing of materials is reduced to the necessary minimum quantities due to its environmental impact and is done when no other (digital) alternatives are possible; eco-printing in FSC paper is strongly encouraged. Other gadgets have so far not been considered necessary or useful.

6.3.6.4 Videos

Six videos illustrating key MAELSTROM's phases are foreseen as part of MAELSTROM's communication strategy. A first introductory video was made in 2021 and projected during *the 1st International Workshop on Removal of Marine Litter and Circular Economy*, held in Venice during the International Boat Show. The video used infographic techniques as no "real" footage could yet be taken. During 2022, three other videos were developed with the guidance of CIMA Research Foundation and the logistical support of the partners responsible for the technologies' development and implementation.

- i) a video illustrating the MAELSTROM app features.
- ii) a video illustrating the Seabed Cleaning Platform in Venice: as we write we are on its final editing's and the video will be published at the start of 2023.
- iii) a video on the implementation of the Bubble Barrier in Vila do Conde – the video is concluded but not yet officially published as the team is still waiting for the Authorities 'authorization to implement the Bubble Barrier. Despite having been partially showed during the UN Ocean Conference event, the full video will be showcased at the start of 2023.

Videos can be seen at the MAELSTROM website under the media section at the MAELSTROM's YouTube channel:

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwGpE7VUFUsoiKdgFuZUvUQ>

Two more comprehensive videos illustrating MAELSTROM's outcomes are expected to be done: i) a video on the second-generation products obtained from collected marine litter: ii) a conclusive video of the project's highlights, to be shown during the MAELSTROM's final conference in 2024.

MAELSTROM

7 ANNEX 1 - Projects and institutions engaged with MAELSTROM's activities

Table 7: EU-funded projects engaged in MAELSTROM's activities

Project name	Link
EU H2020 Claim	https://www.claim-h2020project.eu/
EU H2020 GoJelly	https://gojelly.eu/
EU H2020 SeaClear	https://seaclear-project.eu/
ITA-HR INTERREG MARLESS	https://www.italy-croatia.eu/web/marless
marGnet Consortium	https://www.margnet.eu/it/home/
BlueMed Initiative	http://www.bluedmed-initiative.eu/
H2020 Reliance	https://www.reliance-project.eu/

Table 8: Institutional Actors Engaged with MAELSTROM's activities

Institution	Link
Porto Municipality	https://www.cm-porto.pt/
Venice Municipality	https://www.comune.venezia.it/
Lipor – waste management body in Northern Portugal	https://www.lipor.pt/pt/
Gruppo Veritas - waste management body in Venice	https://www.gruppo-veritas.it/
Aguas do Norte – water management body in Northern Portugal	https://www.adnorte.pt/
Venice Coast Guard	https://www.guardiacostiera.gov.it/organizzazione/direzione-marittima-di-venez
Veneto Region	https://www.regione.veneto.it/
ARPA Veneto (Veneto Environmental Agency)	https://www.arpa.veneto.it/
Provveditorato Interregionale per le Opere Pubbliche per il Veneto, Trentino-Alto Adige e Friuli-Venezia Giulia	http://provveditoratovenetia.mit.gov.it/
Senator Andrea Ferrazzi, member of the Italian Parliament	https://www.senato.it/leg/18/BGT/Schede/Attsen/00032632.htm
WWF Italy	https://www.wwf.it/

Table 9: Private companies engaged with MAELSTROM's activities

Institution	Website
Ecopolietilene Consortium (Italy)	https://ecopolietilene.it/
River Cleaning (Italy)	https://rivercleaning.com/it/
Clera.One (Slovenia)	https://www.clera.one/
WasteShark (The Netherlands)	https://www.wevolver.com/specs/wasteshark

MAELSTROM

Sintol Srl (Italy)	https://sintol.it/
Everwave (Germany)	https://everwave.de/en/
Caracol & NextChem (Italy)	https://nextchem.it
IRIS (Italy)	https://www.irissrl.eu
Fish Flow (The Netherlands)	https://fishflowinnovations.nl/en/
Nanobay (Germany)	https://www.nanobay.com/
Probotica (Croatia)	https://www.probotica.hr/
NNL (Greece)	https://www.oilspillresponse.gr/
Ponikve (Croatia)	http://www.ekootokkrk.hr/en
Empower (Norway)	https://www.empower.eco/
EMI (Italy)	https://emiforpets.it